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Welcome to Father Superior General

Bhausahab Sansare SJ

Rector, Papal Seminary, Punet

On behalf of our Papal Seminary community, I welcome Fr. Arturo Sosa, Superior General of the Society Jesus to our Home of Love. I also extend a warm welcome to Fr. Vernon D'Cunha (RA), Fr. Lisbert D'Souza (RA), Fr. George Pattery (POSA) and Fr. Juan Antonio Alves (Delegate For International Houses in Rome) to our great Home of Love. We put our hands together and welcome them warmly.

As a Superior General, Fr. Arturo Sosa is the head of the Society of Jesus and for us in JDV, he is a Chancellor of JDV. He is the 31st General of the Society of Jesus, elected on Oct 14, 2016. He comes from Venezuela. He is a person of vast experiences in the administration of the Society. He held several responsible posts and portfolios in the Society. He has a wealth of knowledge and wisdom.

He is a very down to earth person. What I recollect from his interventions during General Congregation 36 is that he has a deep love and respect for the poor and the marginalized. To accomplish the mission of God, he believes in collaboration and networking and he urges us to promote it. Another event that has left a great impact on me, which I fondly remember, is after his election as General, he was invited for a meal in

Bellarmino, a Jesuit Formation House in Rome, about 2.5 Kilometers from the Generalate. I was very much touched by his gesture, as he walked to Bellarmino. First he went and greeted the Kitchen Staff. He says, all who are working with us and for us are our mission partners.

Dear Fr. General, you have a personality fitting to an Army General. We thank you very much for visiting us in Papal Seminary, Home of Love, and blessing it with your presence. Formation of Priests in Papal Seminary is a Privileged Mission entrusted to the Society by the Church; it is, in fact, a gift from the Church. Papal Seminary which was started in Kandy, Sri Lanka in 1893 was a fruit of vision and discernment of Pope Leo XIII, with a clear motto: "Your sons, India, will be the Ministers of Salvation for you." Bearing this motto in mind, we form the Priests for the Church, especially the Church in India. Papal Seminary makes efforts to form Priests imbued with the mind and heart of Christ, in communion with the Holy Father and the Universal Church. We form them as the best Priest-collaborators and cooperators with their Bishops in their respective Dioceses.

At Papal Seminary, we are, altogether staff and students 193 community members: among the 193 members 19 are staff members - 14 are Jesuits from 10 different Provinces in India and 5 Diocesan Staff from 5 different Dioceses. Students from three different rites: Latin, Syro Malabar and Malankara from 64 Dioceses and from a couple of religious congregations. Ours is a good collaborative team. Our staff is well qualified and gifted. Our students are also blessed with multiple talents and gifts. They are the chosen ones. Papal Seminary has altogether given 78 prominent leaders (Cardinals, Archbishops and Bishops) and shepherds for

the Church. It has not only given prominent leaders to the Church but also to the Society, e.g. Fr. George Pattery SJ. Thank you for all your support and prayers. Enjoy your stay in Pune.

(Welcome Speech of Rector, Papal Seminary on March 6, 2019)

A Moment of Grace

The visit of Fr General to our Community was a moment of grace to me personally and to the whole Papal Seminary Community. He spent time with us challenging us, motivating us and inspiring his. Through his simple and prophetic words and actions, he has challenged the seminarians to be people of God, who would commit themselves wholeheartedly to the Church and God's people. He was a man of prayer, conviction and freedom.

He challenges us to live our vocation and call in an atmosphere of joy, hope and freedom, like Pope Francis himself.

For Papal Community, it was a moment of grace, where we could experience the loving presence of God in our midst. It was a challenge, guidance and inspiration. May he continue to lead more people to God! May we learn to reach out to the ordinary people, as he has been doing!

Bhauseheb Sansare